

Graphene Synthesis on Cubic SiC/Si Wafers. Perspectives for Mass Production of Graphene-Based Electronic Devices

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ABSTRACT The outstanding properties of graphene, a single graphite layer, render it a top candidate for substituting silicon in future electronic devices. The so far exploited synthesis approaches, however, require conditions typically achieved in specialized laboratories and result in graphene sheets whose electronic properties are often altered by interactions with substrate materials. The development of graphene-based technologies requires an economical fabrication method compatible with mass production. Here we demonstrate for the first time the feasibility of graphene synthesis on commercially available cubic SiC/Si substrates of >300 mm in diameter, which result in graphene flakes electronically decoupled from the substrate. After optimization of the preparation procedure, the proposed synthesis method can represent a further big step toward graphene-based electronic technologies.

KEYWORDS Graphene layer, synthesis, cubic SiC surface

Graphene possesses astonishing electronic properties,^{1,2} like the exceedingly high charge carrier mobility and the occurrence of Dirac fermions.^{3–6} The unique electronic properties of graphene make this material an interesting one for potential applications in electronic devices.^{7–9} Historically the first method of graphene fabrication involved handmade processes such as mechanical exfoliation^{1,10} and was not practical. Other methods are based on graphene films grown on different substrates.

The self-organized growth of carbon atoms into the graphene structure is highly favored on substrates with comparable lattice structure. This was demonstrated for instance for graphene grown on the Ni(111) or Ir(111) surfaces¹¹ and for graphene on the hexagonal 6H- and 4C-SiC(0001) (α -SiC) surfaces.^{12–14} The preparation of graphene layers by the thermal decomposition of α -SiC has been proposed as a promising method for the synthesis of homogeneous, wafer-size graphene layers for technological applications. The method has considerable advantage due to the fact that α -SiC is a large gap semiconductor, which serves as a substrate for the graphene layer.

The substrate considered in this paper, cubic 3C-SiC (β -SiC) is readily grown in large size (>300 mm in diameter)

commercially available Si wafers.^{15–17} Apparently, due to its cubic lattice, β -SiC does not appear suitable for graphene growth. Contrary to common belief, we succeeded in growing high-quality graphene on cubic β -SiC and found that the interaction with the substrate is almost negligible, rendering this system a perfect candidate for future graphene-based electronics.

Bulk β -SiC has zinc blende (sphalerite) structure, i.e., its lattice is composed of two face-centered sublattices shifted with respect to the other in the direction of the cube's diagonal by one-quarter of the diagonal length. Since one sublattice contains silicon atoms and the other carbon atoms, the crystal can be considered as composed of monatomic Si and C planes alternating in the [001] direction. Consequently the (001) surface is either silicon or carbon terminated.

We exposed our sample with a Si-rich surface to a series of annealing cycles with increasing temperature from 1200 K up to 1550 K. Over this process, all known SiC(001) surface reconstructions^{18–20} were observed in the low-energy electron diffraction (LEED) patterns.

We show in Figure 1a the C 1s photoemission (PE) spectra taken at $h\nu = 400$ eV photon energy from the Si-rich β -SiC(001) 3×2 surface, the C-terminated β -SiC(001) $c(2 \times 2)$ surface and the C-rich β -SiC(001) 1×1 surface.

In the case of the Si-rich surface, all carbon atoms occupy equivalent bulk sites. Hence only one component at 282.9 eV binding energy (BE) is present in the PE spectra. Surface

FIGURE 1. Core-level photoemission and near-edge X-ray absorption fine structure spectroscopy. (a) C 1s photoemission taken from the β -SiC(001) at different stages of the surface preparation procedure using $h\nu = 400$ eV photon energy. (b) C 1s photoemission of the C-rich β -SiC(001) 1×1 surface as a function of photon energy. As $h\nu$ is tuned away from the most surface sensitive regime at 325 eV, component B rises which proves its bulk origin. The binding energy of the surface component S equals that found for graphene or graphite. (c) C 1s NEXAFS spectra recorded with increasing retard potential in order to separate bulk and surface features. At the most surface sensitive regime (RP = -200 eV) the spectral shape equals those found for graphene/graphite. (d) With changing incidence angle Θ of the linearly polarized light, a strong anisotropy is found. The behavior of the resonances suggests that the π^* orbitals are collectively oriented parallel to the surface normal and the σ^* orbitals perpendicular, as expected for graphene/graphite.

carbon atoms on the other hand give rise to a second PE component as observed for the C-terminated and the C-rich surface. In the latter case, the surface component is shifted by 1.5 eV toward higher BE. All results are in excellent agreement with those, previously reported for similar superstructures on the β -SiC(001) surface.²¹

In order to verify the origin of both components, we chose a more surface sensitive mode with photon energies between 315 and 350 eV (Figure 1b), where the mean free path of C 1s photoelectrons is considerably reduced reaching its minimum at about $h\nu = 325$ eV. Consequently, the PE intensity of the bulk component is clearly suppressed when approaching 325 eV, whereas the surface peak remains unaffected. Note that the detected energy position and FWHM of the surface component are characteristic for graphite/graphene layers.

Seeking further insight into the nature of the carbon overlayer on β -SiC, we studied its unoccupied electronic states using the near-edge X-ray absorption fine structure (NEXAFS) spectroscopy in partial electron yield mode. The C 1s NEXAFS spectra from the C-rich β -SiC(001) 1×1 surface taken with a set of different retard potentials are shown in Figure 1c. The incident angle of the synchrotron light was 40° relative to the surface normal. A negative retard potential was utilized to adjust the probing depth: at zero retard voltage the detected signal is mainly bulk representative; at -200 V it is mainly surface representative.²⁴

The X-ray absorption spectra of Figure 1c are characterized by two sharp resonances at 285.3 and 291.6 eV and a broad structure at 292.7 eV. These features are characteristic of pristine graphite, and were previously assigned to the π^* , σ_1^* , and σ_2^* resonances, respectively.²⁵ Therefore, the top layer of the C-rich β -SiC(001)- 1×1 surface is definitely graphitic.

For the planar π conjugated systems C $1s \rightarrow \pi^*$ or $1s \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transition probabilities are maximum for the electrical vector perpendicular or parallel to the molecular plane, respectively. Figure 1d shows the surface sensitive (-200 V retard potential) C 1s NEXAFS spectra measured for different incidence angles of the linearly polarized synchrotron light. At grazing incidence, when the direction of the electrical vector is close to the surface normal, the π^* resonance intensity is strongly enhanced. It decreases with increasing incident angle and is largely suppressed for normal incidence. At the same time, the σ^* resonances reveal the opposite angular dependent behavior. The observed polarization dependence is the same as the one of graphene as well as of multilayer graphene, i.e., graphite.

Recently it was shown that the C 1s NEXAFS spectral line shapes may be strongly affected by the interaction with the underlying substrate.²⁶ In our case none of the two sharp resonances (π^* and σ_1^*) is visibly broadened indicating that the “graphitic” layer is hardly sensing the substrate. Nearly the same spectral shape was observed for the weakly bound graphene on Pt(111).²⁶ We therefore conclude that the orbital hybridization and the chemical interaction between the formed graphitic layer and the substrate are weak.

In order to understand which type of carbon overlayer is actually formed, graphite, graphene, or both, we used scanning tunneling microscopy (STM). The topographic STM scans on a large micrometer scale show atomically flat terraces, whose size strongly depends on annealing time and temperature. We obtained two types of atomically resolved STM images (Figure 2). The atomic pattern in Figure 2a points to a graphite structure, where stacking of the monatomic layers gives rise to two nonequivalent atomic sites. Due to the shift between neighboring layers, half of the atoms of the upper layer are located directly above atoms of the lower layer (site A) while the other half are located above the hexagon centers in the lower layer (site B).

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FIGURE 2. Scanning tunneling microscopy. (a) Graphite structure: The two nonequivalent atom sites are colored black and blue, respectively. (b) Graphene structure: All carbon atom sites are equivalent. Hence the characteristic honeycomb pattern shows up.

Accordingly, A sites appear as minima and B sites as maxima in STM images, as demonstrated earlier.²⁷ Figure 2b shows the honeycomb array, characteristic for graphene. Here the stacking-induced asymmetry is absent and consequently all atomic sites are equivalent.

We determined the orientation of the graphene overlayer using the fast Fourier transformation (FFT) of the STM data in Figure 3a and comparing the result with the LEED data of the substrate. From the FFT image in Figure 3b and with the help of the scheme in Figure 3c we conclude that the directions of the reciprocal lattice vectors in graphene deviate from those in SiC by $\Theta_0 + n 60^\circ$, where n is an integer, and the same is true for the real space lattice vectors. We determined Θ_0 for a set of STM images ending up with an average value of $15.3^\circ \pm 2.4^\circ$. This implies that graphene grows with its^{11–20} direction parallel to the [110] direction of the substrate, as illustrated in Figure 3c.

The electronic band structure of the occupied electronic states was examined by angle-resolved photoelectron spectroscopy (ARPES). A typically observed energy-momentum map is shown in Figure 4.

The measured dispersion of the π and σ bands is characteristic of graphene. The additional, nondispersive feature at ~ 3 eV binding energy is very likely caused by the presence of amorphous carbon, not included in the graphene flakes.²⁸ The vertex of the π band at the Γ point lies at ~ 7.9 eV binding energy. This position is correlated with the strength of the graphene–substrate interaction^{11,29} and it is much lower than the one reported for the graphene/ α -SiC system (8.5 eV),³⁰ indicating that the hybridization between graphene and β -SiC is significantly decreased by virtue of the strong lattice mismatch.

Close inspection of the dispersion relation around the K point at $T = 40$ K reveals that, similar to graphene on α -SiC, the Dirac point (E_D) is pushed below the Fermi level^{7,31} to ~ 0.25 eV binding energy. It was demonstrated previously that with growing number of graphene layers E_D gradually shifts back to the Fermi level.⁷ For graphene on α -SiC an E_D value similar to ours was detected when three layers were

FIGURE 3. Orientation of the graphene layer on the SiC(001) surface. (a) STM topographic image of a graphene layer. The crystallographic axes of the cubic substrates were determined via LEED and are indicated by white arrows. (b) FFT of the micrograph in a showing the 6-fold symmetry of the carbon layer and its orientation on the cubic substrate which is included in a as black arrows. (c) Schematic of the graphene layer on the β -SiC(001) surface. The strong lattice mismatch is clearly visible. The inset shows a polar plot of the graphene orientation determined for 15 STM images measured at different sample regions. One cross corresponds to one STM image.

reached. Hence, given the weaker hybridization strength we anticipate that the number of graphene layers in our case does not exceed three and generally varies between one and three. This conclusion is supported also by our STM results.

FIGURE 4. Electronic states in graphene on the β -SiC(001) surface. (a) Overview ARPES intensity map taken along the Γ K direction. (b) ARPES intensity map taken at the K point along the black dotted line.

In summary, we demonstrated for the first time the feasibility of graphene synthesis on cubic β -SiC. A very simple procedure for obtaining graphene on the cheap, commercially available β -SiC/Si wafers of large diameters represents a huge step toward technological application of this material as the synthesis is compatible with industrial mass production. The quality of graphene overlayers was characterized by a number of experimental techniques, indicating very weak interaction with the substrate, crucial for preservation of the astonishing intrinsic properties of graphene. The ability to grow large single-crystal domains is a major target of graphene growth. Despite lattice mismatching, the graphene growth is shown to be guided along the [110] crystallographic direction of the SiC(001) substrate, which might also encourage the formation of reasonable large domains of single-crystal graphene. Therefore as the next step of the investigation we plan to evaluate the size of the graphene grains grown so far on cubic β -SiC and find the approach of formation of relatively large domains, for example, by annealing in argon atmosphere of about 1 bar.³²

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Supporting Information Available. Additional details on β -SiC(001) single crystals, C 1s X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy and NEXAFS measurements, ARPES experiments, and STM micrographs. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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